

References

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We have, therefore, synthesised some *N*-acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines and screened for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae*. Most of them were found to be antifungal.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded using KBr disc. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Substituted-5-chloroacridines¹¹ have been prepared by the cyclisation of substituted-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids¹² by POCl₃. Aryloxybutanoylhydrazines have been prepared by the method of Conti¹³.

N-Acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines: A methanolic solution of substituted-5-chloroacridine (0.001 *M*) and aryloxybutanoylhydrazine (0.001 *M*) was refluxed gently for 3 h and cooled. The product separating out was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised; ν_{\max} 3300-3350 (NH), 1680-1700 (NHCO), 1560-1600 (conjugated cyclic) and 1220-1240 cm⁻¹ (=C-O-C). The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1 along with their physical and antifungal data.

Fungicidal screening: Thirteen compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity

Synthesis of Antifungal *N*-Acridin-5-yl-*N'*- α -aryloxybutanoylhydrazines

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NITROGEN heterocyclics having an unsubstituted nucleus, are seldom antifungal. However, acridine is known to be toxic to spores of various rusts¹. Horsfall and Rich² found acridine to be fairly active against *S. fructicola* and *M. sarcinaeforme*. Acridines have been reported as anthelmintic³, insecticide⁴, rodenticide⁴, acaricide⁴ and fungicide^{5,6}. Acridine derivatives also exhibit antiinflammatory⁷ and carcinogenic⁸ properties. Compounds having aryloxy moiety have been reported as fungicide and plant growth regulator^{9,10}.

TABLE 1—*N*-ACRIDIN-5-YL-*N'*- α -ARYLOXYBUTANOYLHYDRAZINES*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Fungicidal activity (Concentration used 10 ppm)		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	H	H	90	90.2	11.8	11.8	11.2
2.	H	2-Cl	280	98.5	18.0	19.6	17.5
3.	H	4-Cl	200	97.6	20.4	20.8	21.8
4.	H	4-CH ₃	185	81.0	13.5	14.6	12.9
5.	1-Cl	H	265	83.7	19.0	20.4	18.6
6.	1-Cl	2-Cl	100	98.7	—	—	—
7.	1-Cl	4-Cl	140	98.4	27.5	29.8	27.2
8.	1-Cl	4-OH ₂	87	92.0	—	—	—
9.	2-Cl	H	225	83.2	19.6	20.8	18.7
10.	2-Cl	2-Cl	88	98.5	—	—	—
11.	2-Cl	4-Cl	85	73.8	28.4	20.2	27.5
12.	2-Cl	4-OH ₂	259	92.7	—	—	—
13.	1-CH ₃	H	182	86.8	13.4	14.7	13.0
14.	1-CH ₃	2-Cl	245	85.7	—	—	—
15.	1-CH ₃	4-Cl	210	98.0	20.6	22.6	21.5
16.	1-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	262	99.2	—	—	—
17.	2-CH ₃	H	170	99.0	12.8	14.0	18.7
18.	2-CH ₃	2 Cl	220	92.8	—	—	—
19.	2-CH ₃	4-Cl	230	86.8	22.0	24.0	21.4
20.	2-CH ₃	4-OH ₂	295	96.8	18.7	14.8	14.4
					73.5	82.8	78.6

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique¹⁴ at three different concentrations, 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. A commercial fungicide, Blitox 50 WP was tested under similar condition to check the results. The percentage inhibition in fungus growth was expressed as :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C=diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in control after 96 h, and T=diameter of fungus colony (in mm) in the presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

The compounds exhibit low to moderate level of fungicidal activity and were found to possess nearly same level of activity against the three fungi. Compounds having chlorine or methyl group in the acridine ring are more antifungal than those having unsubstituted acridine ring. A change in the position of a group in acridine ring does not show any marked effect towards fungicidal activity. The most active compounds of the series have a chlorine in acridine ring with a 4-chlorophenoxy moiety (compounds 7 and 11).

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Dihydroflavonoids from the Leaves of *Rhus insignis* (Anacardiaceae)

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ALTHOUGH a number of *Rhus* plants have already been examined for flavanoids¹⁻⁶, no work seems to have been done on *Rhus insignis*. We report here the isolation and characterisation of 3,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone, 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavanone, 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone, and 5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavanone, from the leaf extracts of *Rhus Insignis*.

The acetone extracts of dried and powdered leaves (1.5 kg) of *Rhus insignis*, procured from Kurseong, Darjeeling (India), after purification by solvent fractionation and column chromatography (Si gel) were separated into four flavanoidic fractions (Shinoda test)⁷ by plc (Si gel-TEF, 5 : 4 : 1), and termed as RI-I (Rf 0.60, 200 mg), RI-II (Rf 0.64, 300 mg), RI-III (Rf 0.70, 150 mg) and RI-IV (Rf 0.83, 50 mg). The uv spectra of these fractions in methanol, giving only one major absorption peak at 288 nm (band-II), with an inflection at ~320 nm (band-I), and no appreciable shift of band-I in NaOAc/H₃BO₃ or AlCl₃/HCl, showed all of them to be dihydroflavonoids.

Fraction RI-I (m.p. 227-29°) showed the absorption peak of band-II at 276 nm instead of the normal peak at 288 nm. The lower value of the peak (hypsochromic shift of 12 nm) was probably due to the absence of 5-hydroxyl group⁸. The high bathochromic shift of 56 nm in band-II on the addition of NaOAc provided the evidence for the presence of hydroxyl group at C-7 of ring A⁹. RI-I on acetylation with Py-Ac₂O gave an acetate, RI-IA (m.p. 148°). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed acetoxy signals between τ 7.22-7.95 which integrated for 12 protons (four acetoxy). The doublet at τ 3.15 (*J* 2.5 Hz), a double doublet at 3.44 (*J*_{meta} 2.5 Hz) and another doublet at 2.05 (*J*_{ortho} 9 Hz) were assigned to C-8, C-6, and C-5 protons, respectively. The two doublets at τ 4.25 (*J* 11.5 Hz) and 4.70 (*J* 11.5 Hz) were assigned to C-2 and C-3 *trans* protons of ring C. The multiplet at τ 2.60 integrated for 3 protons were attributed to C-2',5',6' protons of ring B, thus establishing a 3',4'-dihydroxy system. The data were in agreement with a structure in which C-3 of a flavanone is substituted with a hydroxyl group. RI-I was thus assigned the structure as 7,3,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone.

The uv absorption peaks of RI-II (m.p. 245°) in MeOH at 288 nm (band-II) with an inflection at